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Does Agricultural Land Moderate the Impact of Climate Change on Food Security in African Countries? Evidence from One and Two-Step GMM

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of climate change, as proxied by carbon dioxide emission on food security, and measured by the food production index (FPI) using an unbalanced panel of 52 African countries. In addition, the study examines the moderating effect of climate change and agricultural land on food security. Using one- and two-step system generalised method of moments (SYGMM), the findings indicate that climate change has a positive and significant effect on food security in the panel of African countries as well as in all the five regions of Africa, namely, Central, East, North, Southern and West Africa. Also, higher or lower agricultural landmass does not necessarily moderate the impact of climate change on food security in Africa, except for South Africa. The policy implication is that plants needed a certain amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission to survive and be healthy in African countries. The study also implies that an increased (CO₂) emission arising from the use of modernised machinery can enhance agricultural productivity, hence ensuring food availability that leads to food security. The suggestion is that African countries should find a way of managing the emission of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere to not impair food security.

Keywords: Climate change, Agricultural land, Energy use, Food security, System GMM

JEL Classifications: C33, O10, Q

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Introduction

The Food Production Index (FPI), as a measure of food security (Osinubi & Apanisile, 2021), covers food crops that are considered edible and contain nutrients excluding coffee and tea. As of 2014, the world FPI was about 125.6 growing from 35.4 to 124.6 between 1965 and 2014. Food production results from agricultural activities, and in the case of modern agriculture, energy consumption is involved in agricultural activities. Considering that there is little or no climate change action in the agriculture sector, agriculture will likely continue to be a major contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and may increase to about 58 per cent by 2050 (Ahmed, et al., 2020). According to the US environmental protection agency in 2018, GHG emissions from the agriculture economic sector accounted for 9.9 per cent of total US GHG emissions. GHG emissions from agriculture have increased by 10.1 per cent since 1990. Food production which is an indicator of food security is a major concern for both developing and developed countries. Long before the outbreak of a pandemic like COVID-19, food insecurity has been a cause of serious concern throughout Africa, particularly sub-Saharan Africa. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization, 239 million people in the African region were malnourished as of 2018 (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2019). These chronic food crises have been driven by factors like economic shocks, climate, and conflict i.e. areas that are severely affected by climate change are characterised by food-insecure people. In this case, food security, according to FAO (2015, p. 53), is defined as “a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life”.

Climate change is a result of carbon emissions ranging from emissions such as carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, fluorinated gases, etc., and other activities like food production. These emissions constitute the carbon footprints resulting from GHG emissions caused by an individual event organisation, industrial activities, etc. Gases including carbon dioxide and methane can be emitted from fossil fuel burning, production of food through agricultural activities, manufacturing of goods, transportation, etc. Food production and its associated activities come with critical environmental externalities due to the use of energy, natural resources, and carbon emitted in the process (Sarkodie et al., 2019). However, the greenhouse gas emissions from the agriculture sector are mostly from food and livestock production aside from the CO₂ the ecosystems remove from the atmosphere which offsets about 20 per cent of emissions from this sector.

The FPI has been found to increase in recent years and this is associated with increased human activities that come with technological, economic, and

human advancement. Furthermore, the FPI which is an indicator of food security is represented in Figure 2 for Africa and it indicates that food production in African countries has increased over time, but not significantly. Considering the climate change effect on food production and agricultural activities, increased food production may imply an increase in agricultural emissions due to an increase in agricultural capacity and fossil fuel burning in the process. This may however be avoided with the adoption of clean technology and sustainable agriculture to ensure adequate food production, and reduce emissions resulting from agricultural activities at the same time. Even though emission like N₂O is cointegrated with economic growth, agricultural land use is found to have a significant effect on N₂O emissions implying the need for countries to optimise their agricultural land use to reduce their N₂O emissions (Haider et al., 2020).

Generally, FPI in Africa has increased over the years which means countries across the continent have increased food production, thus increasing the FPI. For instance, in a country like Angola, its FPI has increased at an increasing rate. However, Angola's FPI from 1960–1990 was between 28 and 37.81. In 1990–2014, Angola's FPI increased continuously from 37.81 to about 100. From 1988–2007, as shown in Figure 1, FPI has increased progressively. According to data from the World Bank indicator, in 2005 Angola's food index was 101.73, 104.82 in 2006, 117.75 in 2007, and 159.41 in 2009 and by 2016 the country's FPI has risen to about 192.85. This implies that even though food production has increased over the years, it may be a result of heightened carbon emissions.

Figure 1: Food Production Index for Angola Between 1988–2007

Additionally, in Figure 2, the FPI, representing food security, and emissions are presented. It indicates that FPI may not have any significant increases but carbon emissions seem to increase. For instance, in Nigeria, the rate of carbon emissions is high compared to the FPI, so it cannot be said that emission increases as the food index increases. In 1972, FPI reduced to 26.96 as compared to 30 in the previous year but FPI fell despite an increase in emissions. For some countries, FPI increases when carbon emission increases. Also, in Cameroon, as carbon emissions increase, FPI seems to increase as well; in 1961, FPI was 25.99 and carbon emission was 271.3 kt and by 2016, when carbon emissions increased to 8291.087kt, FPI had increased to 181.65. Generally, figures from the world bank indicator show that whether changes occur in FPI depends on factors beyond carbon emissions.

Meanwhile, factors that lead to an increase in food production may be beyond emissions but no doubt FPI seems to increase as emission increases.

Figure 2: CO₂ Emissions and Food Production for Some African Countries (1988–2007)

Next, increasing population in a continent such as Africa has triggered the need for increased food production, consumption of energy, economic development. This implies the need for increased agricultural activities and thus emission increase and climate change. However, food waste from production and consumption may lead to an increase in ecological footprints. Meanwhile reducing environmental pressure resulting from food production may imply an inability to improve food security (Sarkodie et al., 2019).

To be specific, reducing carbon emission and mitigating the adverse effects of climate change in countries particularly in Africa, since fossil fuel is generally known to increase emissions and energy consumption, agricultural activities require deliberate efforts. It is necessary to encourage the utilisation of cleaner type energy sources such as renewable energies, adopt agriculture mechanisms that are environmentally friendly and importantly, induce environmental laws and regulations geared towards reducing environmental pollution (Al-Mulali et al., 2016). This study is aimed at investigating whether or not agricultural land moderate the impact of climate change on food security in African countries. The next section discusses the literature and clearly shows the gap this study fills. The third section presents variables, data, model, and method used to achieve the objective of the study, while section four discusses the results with the implication of the findings. The study concludes in section five with vital policy recommendations.

Literature Review

Food Production and Climate Change

Food production may range from farm to processing raw materials from the farm and sea into food in factories fulfilling the consumer demand. The attention should not just be on food production, but also on the food triad, to achieve food security. According to de Almeida Sampaio Guido et al. (2020), this is because the food triad assesses the nutritional, health, and environmental elements of food production (2020). The food triad which is a more informative index can be said to be in line with the sustainable development goals proposed by the United Nations. This is because it integrates three basic spheres for the required changes i.e. health, nutrition, and the environment. Covering these three areas, the food triad is capable of identifying the relevance of consuming natural or minimally processed foods. Therefore, it is important to share this information with the consumers through a medium like food labelling and with the food triad, labelling will be more transparent and give people the opportunity to choose more consciously and this will improve health and environmental conditions (de Almeida Sampaio Guido et al., 2020).

Notwithstanding, GHG emissions from industrial and food production and economic growth are issues of concern although differently. While there are attempts towards reducing carbon emissions, there are policies aimed at improving economic growth and development. In the long run, global greenhouse gases may result in global warming which impedes economic growth. Therefore, to ensure economic growth results in improved environmental quality and reducing climate change, there should be efforts at the global level to introduce and adopt innovations and technology that can lead to increased food production and energy production with little emissions

(Adzawla et al., 2019). Understanding the possible impact of regulating carbon emissions is important for achieving an all-encompassing economic growth and development. With the two-way causal relationship between economic growth and emissions, it is evident that economic activities like food production may also contribute to emissions thus; attempts to reduce emissions may also influence growth. This is why it is necessary to take into consideration all possible carbon emissions means (Mardani et al., 2019).

There are limited studies on the effect of climate change on food security. A pioneering study by Warrick (1988) reveals that an increase in carbon dioxide will lead to about a 10–50 per cent increase in the yields of crops. Similarly, Ejemeyovwi et al. (2018) study the relationship between carbon dioxide emissions and crop production in Africa using a fully modified ordinary least squares method. Their findings show that a significant and positive association exists between carbon dioxide emissions and crop production. This implies that the former is a way of improving the latter. However, the projection from FAO et al. (2018a–g) in Mbow et al. (2019) is that climate change will harm the four pillars of food security. These four pillars include food availability, accessibility, utilisation, and stability. Zewdie (2014) reviews some studies on the impacts of climate change on food security in sub-Saharan Africa. Using food availability as a means of ensuring food security, climate change has both positive and negative effects on food security. For instance, Ludi (2009) establishes that climate change causes a rise and decline in suitable cropland in higher latitudes and lower latitudes, respectively. In the same vein, Badolo and Kinda (2012) confirm that a temperature level between 1 °C and 3 °C is expected to lead to an increase in crop yields in a temperate region, while a decrease in tropical and seasonally dry regions, especially for cereal crops. Whereas, a temperature level that is above 3 °C is expected to reduce crop yields in all regions (see also Liliana, 2005). Also, a study in Ethiopia indicates that food production is severely challenged as a result of climate change as annual food production losses due to climate change rise from year to year (Gutu et al., 2012). Based on existing research, it may be concluded that climate change can have a positive or negative impact on food security.

Energy Consumption, Agriculture and Climate Change

Agriculture has always been an important aspect of any economy and for a continent like Africa with vast fertile land; it is only economically wise to key into agriculture as a means of food production for its fast-rising population. Also, the agriculture sector is capable of contributing positively to the economy. This means that to ensure zero hunger for citizens, it is imperative to sustain the agricultural sector and at the same time work towards reducing global warming by altering farming production techniques and also adopt

agricultural technology methods that are more environmentally friendly (Appiah et al., 2018). In the long run, a two-way causal relationship exists between CO₂ emissions and economic growth and also between carbon emissions and crop production index.

Furthermore, energy consumption may be the total energy used to act or manufacture something. The industrial process of production and agricultural activities like food production requires energy consumption. Energy use results in carbon emissions which mean contributing immensely to environmental degradation and global warming. According to the International Energy Association (IEA), as of 2019, carbon emissions as a result of energy consumption rose by 1.7 per cent making a new record. Energy consumption from the commercial sector contributes more to carbon emissions when compared to the residential sector (Lee & Chong, 2016). Energy consumption may increase emissions while biomass consumption supports the transition to a decarbonised economy by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and thus limiting the demand for fossil fuel. Since there is no single path to reducing emissions and ensuring environmental sustainability, it is important to minimise food waste from the production and consumption of food. This is because it may result in an opportunity to improve food security and reduce environmental pressure from agricultural production (Sarkodie et al., 2019).

On a similar note, the type of energy consumed to a large extent determines the extent of greenhouse gases emitted from energy consumption. Fossil fuel and non-renewable energies generally lead to the emission of CO₂ and this contributes immensely to not only environmental degradation but also global warming. For controlling carbon emissions, a shift from non-renewable energy consumption to renewable energies is indispensable. It is, therefore, necessary for countries in Africa and beyond to cooperate and also facilitate green bond markets between them. This may go a long way to help the carbon emissions mitigating goals of combating global warming and increasing possible investments in clean energy projects (Hanif et al., 2019). Similarly, since coal as a source of energy influences carbon emissions differently from non-renewable energy consumption, there is a need for a change in the energy consumption structure of China and other environmental concerned countries (Long et al., 2015).

Also, the fact that economic growth is a major goal of countries, energy consumption is a huge necessity, and agriculture is a major part of the economy and CO₂ emissions result from the three activities, it is important to consider their relationship both in the short and long run (Wang et al., 2016).

Meanwhile, confirming the interrelationship between income, energy consumption, and emissions, the EKC hypotheses stated the need for

continuous economic growth until the growth leads to a decline in environmental pressure. An inverted U-shaped relationship exists for the agriculture-induced EKC hypothesis of China. This implies that agriculture increases a country's carbon dioxide emissions until the country's economy becomes capable of reducing environmental pressure. This may be achieved when the government, policymakers, and agriculture producers set not only energy-intensive policies and economic activities but also clean agricultural practices to solve environmental problems like global warming (Doğan, 2019). On the same note, the same agriculture-induced EKC hypothesis is valid in an agrarian country like Nigeria. There is a long-run relationship between value-added agriculture and environmental degradation. It is therefore important for government administrators and policymakers to be conscious of the agriculture on the Nigerian economy while taking note of the environmental degradation impact. By so doing, it will be possible to adopt policies that will contribute to a reduction in the continuous bush burning practice by most Nigerian farmers and other pollutants such as fumes from generators and vehicles and also create adequate awareness among farmers on the impact of agricultural emissions on the environment (Agboola & Bekun, 2019). The relationship between agricultural growth and agriculture-induced emissions is increasing continuously and this is due to agriculture intensity effects with little or no emission reduction attempts (Li & Zheng, 2011).

Research Gap

Considering the adverse effect of carbon emissions and the need to ensure environmental sustainability and at the same time curb global warming and climate change, it has become necessary to address issues that lead to emissions. This study investigates whether or not agricultural land moderates the impact of climate change on food security in African countries with evidence from one and two-step GMM. This will go a long way to provide answers to whether or not agricultural land is capable of moderating the impact of climate change on food security. This study fills this gap and provides policy recommendations for Africa. Also, this study became necessary considering the need to increase food production to cover the fast-increasing population which results from urbanisation and world advancement. Energy consumption has become an important issue when addressing the need for economic growth and development. Knowing that energy consumption, food production, and agriculture cannot be substituted for one another, it becomes necessary to investigate whether agricultural land can be capable of moderating the impact of climate change on food security. Further, this study will serve as a reference point for both government and researchers. Also, this study will be relevant for agriculture-emission studies, studies on climate change and food security, studies on FPI, energy studies, and policymakers.

Methodology

Source and Measurements of Variables

In this study, we use unbalanced panel data between 1990 and 2018 for 52 countries in Africa. These countries include Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo Democratic Republic, Congo Republic, Djibouti, Egypt, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Libya, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Seychelles, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. These countries are selected based on data availability, especially for FPI and carbon dioxide emission. In addition, African countries are selected because they are known to be experiencing food insecurity. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization, 239 million people in the African region were malnourished as of 2018 (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2019). All the variables are used in their logarithmic forms for easy interpretations and to reduce non-normality. The variables' source and measurements are discussed in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables Information

Variable	Code	Measurement
Food security	FPI	Food production index (2004–2006 = 100)
Climate change	CO2E	Carbon dioxide emissions, thousands of tonnes
Agriculture land	AGL	Agricultural land, sq. km.
Economic growth	GDP	GDP per capita, constant 2010 dollars
Energy use	EGU	Energy use per capita

Source: www.theglobaleconomy.com

Theoretical Framework

Following Ejemeyovwi et al. (2018), the theories underlying this study are the anthropogenic global warming (AGW) theory and Arthur Lewis's two-sector economy model. The former theory states that climate change is majorly a result of human-induced (anthropogenic) CO₂ emissions. According to Mcrae (2019), AGW theory posits that human industry and agriculture cause “today’s long-term increase in the average temperature of Earth’s atmosphere”. These human industry and agricultural causes come from the Arthur Lewis two-sector economy model where the growth of a less-

developed country originates from a labour transition between two sectors, the capitalist sector (human industry) and the subsistence sector (agriculture). Hence, these theories fit the study in the sense that the capitalist sector through the use of modernised machinery causes CO₂ emissions leading to climate change, which in turn affects the agricultural sector in terms of food production.

Specification of the Model

Going by the theoretical framework, the study modifies the model from the study of Ejemeyovwi et al. (2018) which states that carbon dioxide emission (a measure of climate change) determines crop production. In modifying this, the model of the study is specified in such a way that food production (a measure of food security) is a function of climate change with other control variables. The control variables included are agricultural land, real gross domestic product (GDP), and energy use. Agricultural land is an important determinant of food security. Intuitively, a large landmass is expected to increase food production which then translates to food security in terms of food availability.

Empirically, Olasehinde-Williams et al. (2020) establish that agricultural land increases agricultural productivity, while Ejemeyovwi et al. (2018) indicate that the land tenure system is a good factor in increasing crop production. Real GDP as a measure of economic growth is included because it is expected to spur food security, that is, food production (Ejemeyovwi et al., 2018; Swietlik, 2018). Furthermore, energy use is a plus to agricultural productivity and this follows an intuition that an increase in energy use means an increase in the use of modernised machinery that will aid food production. Also, access to energy will enhance food security and nutrition. These narrations suggest that all the control variables are expected to contribute positively to food security. Equation 1 gives the augmented production function in an econometric form and it summarises the relationship between food security and climate change while controlling for other variables discussed above.

$$\text{Model 1: } FPI_{it} = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 CO_2 E_{it} + \lambda_2 AGL_{it} + \lambda_3 GDP_{it} + \lambda_4 EGU_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

where FPI is food production index and measures food security, CO₂E indicates carbon dioxide emission and measures climate change, AGL is agricultural land, GDP is a real gross domestic product, EGU is energy use, denotes the error term, “i” represents individual countries, and “t” indicates the study period.

The study moves forward in analysing the moderating effect of agricultural land on the impact of climate change on food security. This is done by interacting carbon dioxide emission with the dummy variable from

agricultural land. The dummy variable for agricultural land is obtained using the median values where one is given a value greater than the median value and zero elsewhere. Agricultural land is used given the fact that African countries are endowed with a large landmass. The question to ask is will this large landmass translate to improved food security? Incorporating the interactive term (DCAG) into the model gives Model 2 which is shown in equation 2.

$$\text{Model 2: } FPI_{it} = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 CO_2E_{it} + \lambda_2 AGL_{it} + \lambda_3 GDP_{it} + \lambda_4 EGU_{it} + \lambda_4 DCAG_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (2)$$

where DCAG denotes the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land.

Method of Analysis

In investigating the effect of climate change on food security, we employ static and dynamic panel models. For the static model, the study uses pooled ordinary least square (OLS) and fixed/random effects models, while it uses Arellano and Bond (1991) generalised method of moments for the dynamic panel model. The Pooled OLS does not allow for panel heterogeneities, while the fixed/random effects model allows for heterogeneities (Ibukun & Osinubi, 2020). The fixed effects approach is considered appropriate if the Hausman test is significant, and if otherwise, the random effects approach is appropriate.

The study uses both one-step and two-step system generalised method of moments (SYGMM) in estimating the dynamic relationship between climate change and food security. These GMM estimators are suitable because we have a situation in many countries (N=52) and a short period (T=29). The SYGMM is preferred to the difference GMM because of its recorded efficiency gains, (Baltagi, 2008). The instruments used include the lagged values of dependent and independent variables. A typical dynamic panel model is formulated in equation 3.

$$y_{it} = \phi y_{it-1} + \varphi X_{it} + u_i + \eta_{it} \quad (3)$$

where y_{it} is the dependent variable for individual country i over the period t , X_{it} is the matrix of independent variables for individual country i over the period t , u_i is the individual country-specific effect, and η_{it} is the error term for individual country i over the period t .

To test the validity of the instruments used, Arellano and Bond (1991) recommend two tests. First, there should be no second-order serial correlation in the residuals and this implies that the AR(2) test must not be significant by having a p-value greater than 0.05. Second, the Hansen test of over-identifying restrictions must also be insignificant to accept the null hypothesis of the validity of instruments according to Roodman (2009).

Table 2: Summary Statistics

Group	Statistic	FPI	CO2E	AGL	GDP	EGU
All countries	Mean	1.968	3.370	4.818	3.074	2.723
	Std. Dev	0.121	0.825	0.926	0.446	0.339
	Min.	1.529	1.602	1.176	2.216	0.980
	Max.	2.316	5.702	5.992	4.312	3.526
CAF	Mean	1.974	3.103	4.717	3.198	2.710
	Std. Dev	0.127	0.746	0.964	0.524	0.303
	Min.	1.579	1.681	2.623	2.441	2.294
	Max.	2.316	4.652	5.772	4.312	3.495
EAF	Mean	1.977	3.110	4.645	2.904	2.695
	Std. Dev	0.120	0.570	1.133	0.454	0.239
	Min.	1.529	1.792	1.176	2.216	1.637
	Max.	2.288	4.250	5.699	4.120	3.492
NAF	Mean	1.948	4.611	5.183	3.432	2.897
	Std. Dev	0.119	0.437	0.399	0.274	0.293
	Min.	1.560	3.480	4.422	2.878	2.487
	Max.	2.217	5.358	5.834	4.082	3.526
SAF	Mean	1.985	3.932	5.339	3.541	2.982
	Std. Dev	0.064	0.997	0.602	0.350	0.501
	Min.	1.786	1.602	4.347	2.808	0.980
	Max.	2.140	5.702	5.992	3.896	3.470
WAF	Mean	1.957	3.182	4.811	2.920	2.508
	Std. Dev	0.130	0.656	0.757	0.237	0.257
	Min.	1.568	1.978	2.833	2.436	1.811
	Max.	2.244	5.120	5.867	3.540	2.902

Table 2 gives the summary statistics of the variables under consideration. Regarding FPI, the average FPI for the sample is 1.968. Southern and North Africa have the highest (1.985) and lowest (1.948) average, respectively. The highest FPI is traced to Central Africa (2.316), while the lowest FPI is seen in East Africa. The average CO₂ emission all the countries pooled together is 3.37 with the highest average in North Africa (4.611) and the lowest average in Central Africa (3.103). CO₂ emission oscillates between 1.602 and 5.702 and these are recorded in Southern Africa. The average values of agricultural land (AGL), real GDP (GDP) and energy use (EGU) are 4.818, 3.074 and 2.723, respectively. Among the African regions, Southern Africa has the highest landmass (5.992), whereas East Africa has the lowest land mass (1.176). The highest GDP is found in Central Africa with the lowest GDP in East Africa. In terms of EGU, it hovers between 0.980 (in Southern Africa) and 3.526 (in North Africa). Summarily, the variables of interest are consistent since the mean values lie within the minimum and maximum values. Also, the variables do not move away from their mean values given the smaller values of standard deviation.

To avoid multi-collinearity among the variables, the study uses a pairwise correlation analysis. As presented in Table 3, the relationship between FPI and each of the variables considered is positive and significant except for EGU which shows a significant and negative relationship with FPI at a 5 per cent significant level. A significant positive relationship is established between CO₂ emission and each AGL, GDP EGU; between AGL and EGU; and between GDP and EGU at a 5 per cent level of significance. On the contrary, AGL is negatively and insignificantly related to GDP.

Table 3: Pairwise Correlation Matrix for All Countries

Variable	FPI	CO ₂ E	AGL	GDP	EGU
FPI	1.000				
CO ₂ E	0.247*	1.000			
AGL	0.078*	0.640*	1.000		
GDP	0.151*	0.461*	-0.062	1.00	
EGU	-0.031*	0.779*	0.443*	0.497*	1.00

Note: * denotes $p < 0.05$

Empirical Results

Panel Analyses with Pooled OLS and Fixed Effects Approach

The study employs both static and dynamic panel models to examine the relationship between climate change and food security as shown in Table 4. For the static model, the results from the pooled OLS in column 1 reveal that climate change has no significant effect on food security in African countries.

In the same vein, all the control variables exhibit no significant relationship with food security, except economic growth which has a positive and significant effect on food security. Specifically, a 1 per cent rise in economic growth increases food security by 0.021 per cent. Moderating the effect of agricultural land on the impact of climate change on food security in column 2 does not change the effect of climate change and other control variables on food security. Whereas, the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land has a positive but insignificant impact on food security.

In columns 3 and 4, the results of the fixed effects are presented and the results are improved when compared with pooled OLS. In column 3, all the exogenous variables exert significant positive effects on food security except for energy use whose impact on food security is negative and insignificant. The output elasticities for climate change, agricultural land, and economic growth are 0.210 per cent, 1.820 per cent, and 0.444 per cent, respectively. The interactive term of climate change and agricultural land does not alter the direction of the relationship between food security and all the exogenous variables.

Meanwhile, the interactive term improves the magnitude of the effect of climate change on food security, while it reduces those of the control variables. After moderating the effect of agricultural land on the impact of climate change on food security, the output elasticities become 0.274 per cent, 1.677 per cent, and 0.370 per cent for the individual effect of climate change, agricultural land, and economic growth. Furthermore, the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land increases food security by 0.0002 per cent. The regional dummies document that all the African regions are less food secure in comparison with Central Africa, except Southern Africa which is more food secure than Central Africa. Notably, the coefficients of the regional dummies are not statistically significant, except for the coefficient of North Africa. This implies that food security in North Africa is approximately 3 per cent lower than food security in Central Africa with or without the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land.

Table 4: Panel Analyses on the Effect of Climate Change on Food Security

Variable	Dependent Variable: FPI							
	Pooled OLS (1)	Pooled OLS (2)	Fixed effects (1)	Fixed effects (2)	One step SYGMM (1)	One step SYGMM (2)	Two-step SYGMM (1)	Two-step SYGMM (2)
FPI _{t-1}					0.567*** (0.003)	0.519** (0.024)	0.622** (0.028)	0.573** (0.018)
CO ₂ E	-0.001 (0.899)	0.001 (0.941)	0.210*** (0.000)	0.274*** (0.000)	0.216** (0.039)	0.191* (0.062)	0.216** (0.044)	0.178* (0.065)
AGL	-0.003 (0.543)	-0.004 (0.458)	1.820*** (0.000)	1.677*** (0.000)	0.094 (0.707)	0.188 (0.388)	0.029 (0.918)	0.109 (0.460)
GDP	0.021* (0.071)	0.021* (0.082)	0.444*** (0.000)	0.370*** (0.000)	0.346 (0.347)	0.517* (0.061)	0.237 (0.601)	0.453 (0.143)
EGU	-0.017 (0.203)	-0.018 (0.189)	-0.014 (0.746)	-0.034 (0.416)	-0.213 (0.563)	-0.296 (0.436)	-0.161 (0.726)	-0.270 (0.556)
DCAG		0.00003 (0.278)		0.0002*** (0.000)		0.001 (0.279)		0.001 (0.348)
East Africa	-0.004 (0.679)	-0.004 (0.654)						
North Africa	-0.024** (0.048)	-0.025** (0.025)						

Table 4 Continued

Variable	Pooled OLS (1)	Pooled OLS (2)	Fixed effects (1)	Fixed effects (2)	One step SYGMM (1)	One step SYGMM (2)	Two-step SYGMM (1)	Two-step SYGMM (2)
Southern Africa	0.005 (0.688)	0.004 (0.752)						
West Africa	-0.008 (0.350)	-0.009 (0.322)						
Constant	1.806*** (0.000)	1.807*** (0.000)	-9.464*** (0.000)	-8.692*** (0.000)	-0.969 (0.556)	-1.583 (0.330)	-0.525 (0.785)	-1.076 (0.417)
R-squared	0.663	0.663	0.513	0.675				
F-statistic	42.38*** (0.000)	42.38*** (0.000)	335.46*** (0.000)	291.24*** (0.000)	65.71*** (0.000)	35.54*** (0.000)	58.70*** (0.000)	36.19*** (0.000)
observations	744	744	744	744	702	702	702	702
Hausman test			(0.000)	(0.000)				
No. of instruments					30	31	30	31
Number of countries					36	36	36	36

Table 4 Continued

Variable	Pooled OLS (1)	Pooled OLS (2)	Fixed effects (1)	Fixed effects (2)	One step SYGMM (1)	One step SYGMM (2)	Two-step SYGMM (1)	Two-step SYGMM (2)
AR(1) test					-3.32*** (0.001)	-2.87*** (0.004)	-2.54** (0.011)	-2.64*** (0.008)
AR(2) test					1.27 (0.204)	1.01 (0.313)	1.05 (0.293)	1.07 (0.286)
Hansen test					26.05 (0.351)	25.90 (0.358)	26.05 (0.351)	26.05 (0.358)

Note: (i) *p*-values in parenthesis. (ii) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$ and * $p < 0.1$

Table 5: Regional Analyses on the Effect of Climate Change on Food Security Using a Fixed/Random Effects Approach

Variable	Dependent Variable: FPI									
	Central Africa (1)	Central Africa (2)	East Africa (1)	East Africa (2)	North Africa (1)	North Africa (2)	Southern Africa (1)	Southern Africa (2)	West Africa (1)	West Africa (2)
CO2E	0.198*** (0.000)	0.206*** (0.000)	0.302*** (0.000)	0.324*** (0.000)	0.337** (0.039)	0.381** (0.019)	0.034*** (0.000)	0.038*** (0.000)	0.343*** (0.000)	0.357*** (0.000)
AGL	8.769*** (0.000)	8.477*** (0.000)	1.892*** (0.000)	1.838*** (0.000)	0.661 (0.101)	0.489 (0.223)	-1.149*** (0.000)	-1.163*** (0.000)	1.212*** (0.000)	1.149*** (0.000)
GDP	0.431*** (0.001)	0.474*** (0.001)	0.464*** (0.000)	0.417*** (0.000)	-0.128 (0.410)	-0.062 (0.691)	0.561*** (0.000)	0.572*** (0.000)	1.355 (0.119)	1.319 (0.125)
EGU	0.235*** (0.003)	0.233*** (0.003)	-0.539*** (0.000)	-0.547** (0.000)	0.830** (0.002)	0.747** (0.004)	-0.137*** (0.005)	-0.136*** (0.005)	0.071 (0.418)	0.069 (0.430)
DCAG		0.001* (0.071)		0.001* (0.078)		0.002** (0.027)		0.00002 (0.220)		0.001** (0.040)
Constant	-45.122*** (0.000)	-43.807*** (0.000)	-8.369*** (0.000)	-8.022*** (0.000)	-5.032*** (0.000)	-4.343*** (0.020)	1.013*** (0.001)	1.013*** (0.001)	-5.892*** (0.000)	-5.892*** (0.000)
R-squared	0.654	0.663	0.786	0.790	0.728	0.740	0.3401	0.3401	0.806	0.811
Hausman test	(0.006)	(0.000)	(0.006)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.525)R	(0.317)R	(0.006)	(0.000)

Table 5 Continued

Variable	Central Africa (1)	Central Africa (2)	East Africa (1)	East Africa (2)	North Africa (1)	North Africa (2)	Southern Africa (1)	Southern Africa (2)	West Africa (1)	West Africa (2)
F-statistic	59.99*** (0.000)	49.53*** (0.000)	186.64*** (0.000)	151.50*** (0.000)	73.42*** (0.000)	61.90*** (0.000)			179.47*** (0.000)	147.14*** (0.000)
Wald test							73.41*** (0.000)	73.41*** (0.000)		
Observations	138	138	217	217	120	120	82	82	187	187
No. of countries	7	7	10	10	6	6	4	4	10	10

Note: (i) *p*-values in parenthesis. (ii) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$ and * $p < 0.1$. (iii) *R* indicates that random effect is appropriate

The diagnostic tests for both pooled OLS and fixed effects indicate that the exogenous variables are jointly significant in explaining food security at a 1 per cent level of significance. Also, the R-squared suggests that over 50 per cent variation in food security is explained by the exogenous variable. The significant p-values of the Hausman test in columns 3 and 4 accept the null hypothesis that the fixed effects approach is appropriate and this justifies its employment over the random-effects approach.

Panel Analyses with System Generalised Method of Moments

To solve the problem of endogeneity, omitted variables, and simultaneity, the study uses both a one-step and two-step dynamic SYGMM. The results from columns 5–8 show that the models are dynamic since the previous value of food security, as expected, increases its present value with or without the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land. Specifically, a 1 per cent increase in the past value of food security will increase its current value by over 0.50 per cent. In the same way, a change in climate change is expected to increase food security as seen in columns 5–8. In specific terms, a positive relationship exists between climate change and food security with a 0.216 per cent change in food security due to a 1 per cent change in climate change (see columns 5 and 7).

Agricultural land and economic growth positively influence food security but in an insignificant manner, while energy use has a negative and insignificant effect on food security. The moderating effect of agricultural land on the impact of climate change on food security does not affect the direction of the effect of climate change on food security, rather it decreases slightly the magnitude of the effect of climate change on food security. Also, for the control variables, the interactive term only changes the insignificant positive effect of economic growth on food security to a significant positive effect while using one-step SYGMM. The output elasticities reduce to 0.191 per cent and 0.178 per cent in columns 6 and 8, respectively. The effect of the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land on food security is positive but not significant.

According to the diagnostic results in columns 5–8, the F-statistics show that the exogenous variables jointly explain food security at a 1 per cent level of significance. Also, there is no second-order serial correlation in the residuals based on the insignificant p-values of AR(2) tests in all the models. In testing the validity of the instruments used, it is observed that the instruments are valid since the (i) number of instruments is less than the number of groups, and (ii) Hansen tests are insignificant at either 1 per cent or 5 per cent level of significance.

Regional Analyses with Fixed/Random Effects Approach

Table 5 reports the effect of climate change on food security in all the five African regions, that is, Central, East, North, Southern, and West Africa. Importantly, we accept the alternative hypothesis that the fixed effects method is appropriate in all the regions, except in Southern Africa where the null hypothesis that the random effects approach is appropriate is accepted. The diagnostic tests show that food security is jointly explained by all the exogenous variables at a 1 per cent significant level using F-statistic and Wald Chi-squared tests. The results of the R-squared imply that the variation in food security is explained by approximately 66 per cent, 79 per cent, 74 per cent, 34 per cent and 81 per cent in Central, East, North, Southern and West Africa, respectively.

From the fixed/random effects in all the regions, climate change has a positive effect on food security with or without the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land. This is in line with the results from the full sample using both SYGMM and fixed effects approaches. Without the interactive term (DCAG), a 1 per cent rise in climate change increases food security by 0.198 per cent, 0.302 per cent, 0.337 per cent, 0.034 per cent and 0.343 per cent Central, East, North, Southern and West Africa, in that order. The interactive term only improves the coefficient values to 0.206 per cent, 0.324 per cent, 0.381 per cent, 0.038 per cent and 0.357 in that order. Relatedly, agricultural land, as expected, has a positive and significant effect on food security in these regions with or without the interactive term, except in North Africa where its positive effect on food security becomes insignificant with or without the interactive term. The output elasticities range between 0.661 per cent and 8.769 per cent with the exclusion of the interactive term, and between 0.489 per cent and 8.477 per cent with the inclusion of the interactive term. Contrarily, agricultural land in Southern Africa reduces food security by 1.149 per cent (without DCAG) and 1.163 per cent (with DCAG).

Furthermore, economic growth in Central, East, Southern, and West Africa increases food security with elasticities hovering between 0.417 per cent and 1.319 per cent. Meanwhile, the effect of economic growth on food security in West Africa is insignificant. On the other hand, economic growth has a negative and insignificant effect on food security in North Africa. Food security increases with an increase in energy use in Central, North and West Africa but the effect is insignificant in West Africa. However, the effect of energy use on food security is negative and significant in East and Southern Africa. With or without the interactive term, the elasticities are approximately 0.20 per cent, -0.54 per cent, 0.80 per cent, -0.14 per cent and 0.07 per cent in Central, East, North, Southern and West Africa, respectively. Finally, the interactive term of climate change and agricultural land increases food

security by 0.001 per cent in Central, East and West Africa, and by 0.002 per cent in North Africa. The interactive term is found to be positive and insignificant in Southern Africa with an output elasticity of 0.00002 per cent.

Discussion of Findings

Pooling all the countries together, the positive and significant result that is established between climate change and food security tends to align with the work of Ejemeyovwi et al. (2018) that increased climate change is related to improved food security. This finding could be explained by the fact that some plants (including edible plants) need a certain amount of carbon dioxide emission to survive and be healthy in African countries, thus, a positive relationship between climate change and food security (Warrick, 1988). The same results are found for each of the regions in Africa. This implies that climate change is an important driver of agricultural productivity, particularly food production (or food availability) which is an indicator of food security in Africa. Another point of the argument is that increased carbon dioxide emissions arising from the use of mechanised machinery such as bulldozers, tractors, disc plows, seed mills, and plows would result in a higher level of agricultural productivity, hence ensuring food availability that leads to food security (see also of Ejemeyovwi et al., 2018).

Following the panel analysis using fixed effects, agricultural land increases food security in Africa and all the regions in Africa, except in Southern Africa where its effect on food security is negative despite having the highest agricultural landmass among the regions. The positive effect supports the empirical evidence from the findings of Olasehinde-Williams et al. (2020) and Ejemeyovwi et al. (2018) that establish that land has a crucial role to play in achieving food security. The negative effect could be attributed to the fact that agricultural land in Southern Africa is vulnerable to water reduction. This narration confirms the findings of Mabhaudhi et al. (2018) that the region faces water scarcity that will harm food production as confirmed by this study. In the same vein, economic growth will increase food security in the panel of African countries and Central, East, and North Africa based on the regional analyses using pooled OLS and fixed effects approach. Simply put, improved economic growth is associated with higher food security and this is in tandem with the study of Swietlik (2018) who opines that the basic condition for improvement in world food security is economic growth and growth in real incomes, especially in poorer countries like Africa.

Energy use as one of the control variables does not significantly affect food security pooling the countries together. However, when accounting for the effect of energy use on food security in each region, its effect becomes significant and positive in Central and North Africa, and negative in East

Africa and Southern Africa. The positive impact implies that improved access to energy will enhance people's food security (World Food Programme, WFP, 2019). The negative result is against the a priori expectation and WFP' report. Finally, the effect of interactive terms of climate change and agricultural land on food security reveals that higher or lower agricultural landmass does not necessarily moderate the impact of climate change on food security in Africa, particularly in Central, East, North and West Africa.

Concluding Remarks

Climate change is an important driver of agricultural productivity, particularly food production (or food availability) which is an indicator of food security in the world, Africa inclusive. This assertion births this study in examining the impact of climate change, as proxied by carbon dioxide emission, on food security, as measured by FPI using an unbalanced panel of 52 African countries. The findings of this study are based on the SYGMM as it helps in solving the problems of endogeneity, simultaneity, and omitted variables. The results from the one-step and two-step SYGMM suggest that climate change has a positive and significant effect on food security in the panel of African countries as well as in all the five regions of Africa, that is, Central, East, North, Southern, and West Africa. Also, higher or lower agricultural landmass does not necessarily moderate the impact of climate change on food security in Africa, particularly in Central, East, North, and West Africa.

The policy implication is that plants needed a certain amount of carbon dioxide emission to survive and be healthy in African countries (Warrick, 1988) and also, increased carbon dioxide emission arising from the use of modernised machinery such as bulldozers, tractors, disc plows, seed mills, and plows would result in a higher level of agricultural productivity, hence ensuring food availability that leads to food security. Also, the need to increase mechanised farming becomes imperative in a post-pandemic world, as many economies increasingly attempt to manage scarce resources efficiently. This suggests also that, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, favourable trade agreements need to be set for Africa, to provide a clear path to economic recovery.

The suggestion emanating from this finding is that African countries should find a way of managing the emission of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere to not impair food security since carbon dioxide emission can as well reduce food production through increasing temperature, flood, drought, and varying weather conditions. In the post-pandemic era, a follow-up study to this will be to disaggregate variables across two time periods and investigate how this result will differ when crisis events such as the COVID-19 pandemic are

considered in the modelling process. In addition, future studies can examine the (i) direction of causality between climate change and food security in African countries, (ii) threshold value of carbon dioxide emission needed for plants to survive and be healthy, and (iii) the same research gap in different groups of countries.

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